

Synthesis and spectral characterization of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of trioxadiazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and benzil or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil

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Abstract : 1 + 1 Cyclocondensation of α -diketones such as benzil, 4,4'-dimethylbenzil with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane in the presence of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} as templates has yielded complexes of the type [NiLCl]Cl, [CuL(NO₃)](NO₃) and [ZnLCl₂] (where L = 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycle). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductances, FAB mass, IR, electronic and ¹H NMR spectra.

Keywords : α -Diketones, nickel, copper, zinc, macrocyclic complexes, electronic spectra, ¹H NMR spectra.

Introduction

Due to the applications of oxazamacrocyclic complexes in biological and catalytic fields¹⁻³ and as sensors for cations, anions and molecular scaffolds for materials and biological models⁴⁻⁶ a number of such complexes e.g. Cu^{II} complexes of 3,4:9,10-dibenzo-1,12-diaza-5,8-dioxacyclotetradecane and Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of trioxadiazamacrocycles derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and tris(3-aminopropyl)amine have been synthesized^{7,8}. Template condensation of isatin or glyoxal with 1,8-diaminonaphthalene in the presence of Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} ions resulted in the formation of macrocyclic complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} respectively^{9,10}. Ilhan *et al.*¹¹ have synthesized Zn^{II} complex of the macrocycle derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and 1,6-bis(2-formylphenyl)hexane. Keeping this in view, we have reported earlier Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of dioxadiazamacrocycles^{12,13} and in the present paper, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of trioxadiazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil are described.

Experimental

NiCl₂·6H₂O (Merck), Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O (Merck) and ZnCl₂ (Merck) were of AR grade. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (Aldrich), benzil (Sisco), 4,4'-dimethylbenzil (Sisco) were used as such. n-Butanol (Sisco) and DMSO were distilled before use.

Analytical methods and measurements : Ni, Cu and Zn were determined by standard methods¹⁴. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304. The IR spectra (KBr) in the region 400-4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-d₆ on a JEOL AL-300 spectrometer at 300 MHz using TMS as a reference.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O (4.2 mmol, 0.903 g) was dissolved in 20 ml of n-butanol with constant stirring. The butanoic solution of benzil (4.2 mmol, 0.418 g) was added dropwise. The butanoic solution of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (4.2 mmol, 0.919 g) was added with constant stirring. The contents were refluxed for 7-8 h. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, Cu^{II} complex of other oxazamacrocyclic derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil was synthesized. The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of oxazamacrocycles with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil were also synthesized by similar procedure.

Results and discussion

The reactions of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ZnCl_2 with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 17-membered oxazamacrocycles (Schemes 1 and 2). The complexes of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are green, blue and white solids respectively. These complexes are stable at room temperature and decompose at higher temperature. These are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile and DMF but are soluble in DMSO. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductances : Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions in DMSO of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of oxazamacrocycles are observed in the range $55\text{--}65 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating them to be 1 : 2 electrolytes¹⁵. Thus the chloride groups and nitrate groups which are coordinated in solid state are displaced in solution by the solvent molecules¹⁶. Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of Zn^{II} complexes in DMSO are found in the range $12\text{--}15 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating them to be non-electrolytes. Thus the chloro groups are coordinated to zinc giving tetrahedral geometry as the ether oxygens do not coordinate¹⁷.

IR spectra : IR spectra of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} com-

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} .

Scheme 2. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} .

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of trioxadiazamacrocycles

Compd.	Colour	Yield (%)	Decomp. temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Analyses (%) :		Molar conductances ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	IR $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (cm^{-1})
				Found (Calcd.)			
				M	N		
$[\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{NiCl}]\text{Cl}$	Green	61.7	219	11.10 (11.19)	5.19 (5.30)	57	1565
$[\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{NiCl}]\text{Cl}$	Green	54.0	223	10.61 (10.70)	4.93 (5.10)	59	1572
$[\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)]\text{NO}_3$	Blue	64.9	230	10.76 (10.92)	9.49 (9.63)	63	1580
$[\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)]\text{NO}_3$	Blue	68.3	235	10.26 (10.42)	9.03 (9.18)	65	1595
$[\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ZnCl}_2]$	White	49.0	236	12.18 (12.30)	5.09 (5.27)	12	1562
$[\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ZnCl}_2]$	White	53.0	239	11.65 (11.80)	4.93 (5.06)	15	1568

plexes show medium to strong intensity bands in the region 1562–1595 cm^{-1} which are assigned to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ resulting from the condensation of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups of α -diketones with the NH_2 groups of the diamines^{18,19}. The complexes exhibit no absorption bands at 1700 cm^{-1} and 3200–3400 cm^{-1} which could be ascribed to unreacted $\text{C}=\text{O}$ or NH_2 group respectively²⁰. In Cu^{II} complexes, appearance of bands at 1485 cm^{-1} and 1385 cm^{-1} confirms the presence of both ionic and coordinated (monodentate) nitrate groups respectively^{21,22}.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes exhibit bands in the region 16616–16960 cm^{-1} and 26320–27770 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively indicating an octahedral geometry around metal atom with D_{4h} symmetry²³. The Cu^{II} complexes show broad bands in the region 16110–16950 cm^{-1} indicating distorted octahedral geometry around metal atom due to Jahn Teller distortion. The distortion usually leads to an elongation of two bonds giving four short and two long Cu-L distances²⁴.

¹H NMR spectrum : ¹H NMR spectrum of Zn^{II} complex $[\text{Zn}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$ has been recorded. A peak at δ 2.52 ppm is observed due to the residual methyl protons of the solvent DMSO.

In free trioxadiazine, NCH_2 protons give a triplet at

δ 3.10 ppm and OCH_2 protons appear as a triplet at δ 2.83 ppm. In free macrocycles, though not isolated, the peak due to NCH_2 protons appears as a triplet at high field (δ 2.46 ppm) which supports the coordination of nitrogen atoms to the metal atom. The peak due to OCH_2 protons remains almost unaffected (δ 2.94 ppm) indicating that the oxygen atoms do not participate in coordination. In free benzil ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5^a\text{COCOC}_6\text{H}_5^a$), the aromatic protons (C_6H_5) exhibit a multiplet at δ 7.01 ppm. In the complex, C_6H_5^a protons of the ketone moiety give rise a multiplet at δ 7.61 ppm²⁵. CH_2^b protons of the amine residue are at higher field (δ 1.31 ppm) supporting the coordination of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group with metal atom and appear as a pentet. Linody *et al.*²⁶ have determined the X-ray crystal structure of $\text{Zn}(\text{L})_2$ (where $\text{L} = 1,4\text{-diaz-8,11-diox-6,7:12,13-dibenzocyclotetradecane}$) in which two nitrogen atoms of the macrocycle together with two iodo groups coordinate to Zn atom and oxygen atoms remain uncoordinated indicating tetrahedral geometry.

FAB mass spectra : The FAB mass spectra of two Ni^{II} complexes $[\text{Ni}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{Ni}\{(\text{MePh})_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, one Cu^{II} complex $[\text{Cu}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}(\text{NO}_3)](\text{NO}_3)$ and one Zn^{II} complex $[\text{Zn}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$ have been recorded using NBA matrix. The m/z values and the relative abundances of various fragments are given in Table 2. Peaks

Table 2. m/z Values and % relative intensities of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of macrocycles

Assignment	$[\text{Ni}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{-dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ (%)	$[\text{Ni}\{(\text{MePh})_2[17]\text{-dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ (%)	$[\text{Cu}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}(\text{NO}_3)](\text{NO}_3)$ (%)	$[\text{Zn}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{-dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$ (%)
$[\text{M}]^+$	8.8	5.3	8.4	26.3
$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	3.5	3.3	2.6	23.7
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}]^+$	5.3	3.9	–	26.3
$[\text{M}-2(\text{NO}_3)_2]^+$	–	–	10.5	–
$[\text{L}]^+$	10.5	3.9	10.5	5.3
$[\text{L}+\text{H}]^+$	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3
$[\text{L}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	2.6	–	15.8	26.3
$[\text{L}-2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]^+$	5.3	–	100	10.5
$[\text{L}-\text{CH}_3]^+$	–	5.3	–	–
$[\text{L}-\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4]^+$	–	5.3	–	–
$[\text{L}-\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3]^+$	–	3.9	–	–
$[\text{L}-2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)]^+$	–	5.3	–	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	5.3	–	–	15.8
$[\text{M}-2(\text{NO}_3)-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	–	–	15.8	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]^+$	10.5	–	–	10.5
$[\text{M}-2(\text{NO}_3)-2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]^+$	–	–	21.1	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{CH}_3]^+$	–	3.9	–	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4]^+$	–	6.6	–	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3]^+$	–	5.3	–	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)]^+$	–	15.8	–	–

Note

at m/z 136, 137, 154, 280, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. All the complexes show peaks corresponding to molecular ion $[M]^+$ and free macrocycle $[L]^+$ which confirm the formation of macrocyclic complexes. The fragmentation pattern of the complex $[Zn\{Ph_2[17]diene-N_2O_3\}Cl_2]$ has been discussed in detail (Scheme 3). The complex exhibits molecular ion $[M]^+$ (a) peak at m/z 530 (26.3%). Fragment (b) is produced due to the loss of one chloride from molecular ion (a) and appears at m/z 493 (15.8%). By the loss of another chloride, peak due to

fragment (c) is observed at m/z 458 (26.3%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of (c) :

(A) : In this pathway, the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of two phenyl groups from fragment (c) gives peaks at m/z 381 (15.8%) and 304 (10.5%) due to the species (d) and (e) respectively. Loss of Zn from species (e) finally gives the species (f) at m/z 240 (10.5%).

(B) : In this pathway, the loss of the metal ion from the fragment (c) gives a peak at 394 (5.3%) due to free

Scheme 3. Fragmentation pattern of $[Zn\{Ph_2[17]diene-N_2O_3\}Cl_2]$.

Table 3. Calculations of relative abundances of molecular ion peaks $[M]^+$ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	m/z	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{64}Zn^{35}Cl_2$	528	$(0.48)(0.76)^2 = 0.277$	0.277	83.7
2.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{64}Zn^{35}Cl^{37}Cl$	530	$(0.48)(0.76)(0.24) \times 2 = 0.175$		22.0
3.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{66}Zn^{35}Cl_2$	530	$(0.27)(0.76)^2 = 0.156$	0.331	100
4.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{64}Zn^{37}Cl_2$	532	$(0.48)(0.24)^2 = 0.028$		26.3
5.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{66}Zn^{35}Cl^{37}Cl$	532	$(0.27)(0.76)(0.24) \times 2 = 0.098$		18.3
6.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{68}Zn^{35}Cl_2$	532	$(0.18)(0.76)^2 = 0.104$	0.230	69.5
7.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{66}Zn^{37}Cl_2$	534	$(0.27)(0.24)^2 = 0.016$		6.4
8.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{68}Zn^{35}Cl^{37}Cl$	534	$(0.18)(0.76)(0.24) \times 2 = 0.065$	0.081	24.5
9.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{68}Zn^{37}Cl_2$	536	$(0.18)(0.24)^2 = 0.010$	0.010	3.0

Table 4. Calculations of relative abundances of fragment $[C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3ZnCl]$ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	m/z	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{64}Zn^{35}Cl$	493	$(0.48)(0.76) = 0.365$	0.365	100
2.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{64}Zn^{37}Cl$	495	$(0.48)(0.24) = 0.115$		15.8
3.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{66}Zn^{35}Cl$	495	$(0.27)(0.76) = 0.205$	0.320	87.7
4.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{66}Zn^{37}Cl$	497	$(0.27)(0.24) = 0.065$		13.9
5.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{68}Zn^{35}Cl$	497	$(0.18)(0.76) = 0.137$	0.202	55.3
6.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{68}Zn^{37}Cl$	499	$(0.18)(0.24) = 0.043$	0.043	11.8

Table 5. Calculations of relative abundances of fragment $[C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3Zn]$ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	m/z	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{64}Zn$	458	0.48	100	26.3
2.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{66}Zn$	460	0.27	56.3	14.8
3.	$C_{24}H_{30}N_2O_3^{68}Zn$	462	0.18	37.5	9.9

Table 6. Calculations of relative abundances of fragment $[C_{18}H_{25}N_2O_3Zn]$ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	m/z	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	$C_{18}H_{25}N_2O_3^{64}Zn$	381	0.48	100	15.8
2.	$C_{18}H_{25}N_2O_3^{66}Zn$	383	0.27	56.3	8.9
3.	$C_{18}H_{25}N_2O_3^{68}Zn$	385	0.18	37.5	5.9

Table 7. Calculations of relative abundances of fragment $[C_{12}H_{20}N_2O_3Zn]$ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	m/z	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	$C_{12}H_{20}N_2O_3^{64}Zn$	304	0.48	100	10.5
2.	$C_{12}H_{20}N_2O_3^{66}Zn$	306	0.27	56.3	5.9
3.	$C_{12}H_{20}N_2O_3^{68}Zn$	308	0.18	37.5	3.9

*($a_A \cdot x^A + b_A \cdot y^A + c_A \cdot z^A + \dots$)ⁿ ($a_B \cdot x^B + b_B \cdot y^B + c_B \cdot z^B + \dots$)^m....., where a_A, b_A, c_A etc. are the fractional abundances of the isotopes x^A, y^A, z^A of element A and n is the number of atoms of A present in the ion; similarly for m atoms of B and so on.

macrocyclic (g). Subsequent loss of two phenyl groups from fragment (g) gives peaks at m/z 317 (26.3%) and 240 (10.5%) due to the species (h) and (f) respectively.

The spectrum of the complex $[\text{Zn}\{\text{Ph}_2[17]\text{diene-N}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$ has been analysed on the basis of isotopic abundances of different nuclei particularly those of Zn (^{64}Zn , ^{66}Zn and ^{68}Zn) and Cl (^{35}Cl and ^{37}Cl). Various isotopic peaks have been observed but only the most abundant peaks have been considered while discussing the fragmentation pattern. These isotopic peaks have been analysed on the basis of theoretical calculations (Table 3). The calculation for this complex shows the molecular ion isotopic peaks at m/z 528, 530, 532, 534 and 536 due to the different isotopes of Zn and Cl and their relative abundances are 22.0%, 26.3%, 18.3%, 6.4% and 0.8% respectively; the peak at m/z 536 is neglected due to its low abundance. In the spectrum, the relative abundances of the peaks at m/z 528, 530, 532 and 534 with respect to base peak are 18.4%, 26.3%, 10.5% and 5.3% which are close to the calculated values. Similar calculations for other fragments of this complex are given in Tables 4–7. Thus the mass spectral studies strongly support the formation of macrocyclic complexes.

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